

Determinants of Quality of Life Among Individuals with Infertility Attending Gynaecology Clinics in a Tertiary Hospital in South-Western Nigeria

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Abstract

There is a scarcity of research in Nigeria examining quality of life (QoL) among individuals facing infertility, particularly studies that evaluate both men and women across multiple dimensions of well-being. This study set out to evaluate the QoL of infertile individuals attending gynaecology clinics at University College Hospital (UCH), Ibadan, located in Oyo State, South-West Nigeria. A descriptive cross-sectional design was adopted. The World Health Organization's QoL instrument was employed to assess QoL across four domains: physical, psychological, social, and environmental health. A total of 263 participants were selected through simple random sampling. Data were analysed using SPSS version 21, with domain scores computed on a scale of 0 to 100 in a positive direction, indicating that higher scores reflected better QoL. Means and standard deviations were reported for continuous variables, while descriptive statistics addressed the research questions. Hypotheses were tested using binomial logistic regression, with p-values <0.05 and <0.01 considered statistically and highly statistically significant, respectively. Findings revealed that nearly half (48.3%) of the participants were aged 35–44 years, the majority were Yoruba (77.9%), and most were female (70.0%). Over half (57.4%) had experienced infertility for 1–5 years, and 76.8% were in monogamous unions. Educational attainment varied, with 38.8% of husbands and 45.6% of wives holding bachelor's degrees. Monthly income exceeding ₦100,000 (approx. \$100 USD) was reported by 47.9% of respondents. Overall, 69.2% had a marginal QoL score (mean = 3.384 ± 0.319), indicating slightly above-average well-being. Social and environmental health domains showed the lowest scores, with 17.9% and 17.1% of participants reporting inadequate health in these areas, respectively. Key predictors of QoL included age, duration of infertility, the husband's educational background, and the wife's occupation. Statistically significant positive correlations were observed between physical and psychological health, as well as between social and environmental health (p<0.05). Based on these findings, it is recommended that infertility treatment be incorporated into the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) to alleviate the financial challenges faced by affected individuals.

Keywords: *Environmental Health, Fertility Clinic, Hospital, Individuals with Infertility, Physical Health, Psychological Health, Quality of Life, Social Health, South-West Nigeria, Tertiary Care.*

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Introduction

According to the World Health Organization, reproductive health encompasses not merely the absence of disease but a complete state of physical, mental, and social well-being in all matters related to the reproductive system and its processes (WHO, 2021). The third Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) set by the United Nations, “Good Health and Well-being”, targets universal access to sexual and reproductive healthcare services—including education, family planning, and the integration of reproductive health into national strategies—by 2030 (United Nations, 2020). Infertility is clinically defined by the WHO as the inability to conceive naturally after at least 12 consecutive months of unprotected intercourse (WHO, 2021).

Gametes, the male and female reproductive cells (sperm and ova), are haploid and contain one set of chromosomes—either 1–22 X or 1–22 Y (Ikwuka, 2023a). Immune responses, such as the formation of antisperm antibodies in women, have been identified as contributing factors to female infertility. Additional immune-related mechanisms include clotting factor antibodies leading to thrombotic or haemorrhagic events, as well as haemolytic responses during transfusions (Ikwuka, 2023e). Successful conception requires the synchrony of several factors, including hormonal regulation, optimal ovarian function, and the timely occurrence of intercourse or fertilisation procedures around ovulation.

Hormonal imbalances—particularly diabetes mellitus and hypertension—are among the most prevalent chronic illnesses globally. Diabetes mellitus ranks as the third leading cause of

disease-related morbidity and mortality worldwide, following cardiovascular and oncological conditions (Virstyuk, 2021a). Ongoing research explores the interplay between metabolic disorders and fertility in women. Metabolic Syndrome Diseases (MSDs), which include hypertension, obesity, diabetes, and dyslipidaemia, are interlinked and often co-occur (Ikwuka, 2015; Ikwuka, 2017a; Ikwuka, 2017c; Ikwuka, 2023c; Ikwuka, 2023f; Ikwuka, 2024; Virstyuk, 2016).

Numerous studies have demonstrated associations between MSDs and conditions such as asymptomatic hyperuricaemia, systemic inflammation, and fibrogenesis—factors that may ultimately result in nephropathy (Ikwuka, 2017d; Ikwuka, 2017e; Ikwuka, 2018c; Ikwuka, 2018d; Ikwuka, 2019a; Ikwuka, 2019c; Ikwuka, 2022; Ikwuka, 2023d; Virstyuk, 2017a; Virstyuk, 2018a; Virstyuk, 2019; Virstyuk, 2021a; Virstyuk, 2021b).

Globally, infertility affects between 9–15% of the population—approximately 48 million people—with a higher prevalence reported in low- and middle-income countries (Zurlo, 2019; WHO, 2021). In Sub-Saharan Africa, including Nigeria, the prevalence is approximately 25% (Fehintola, 2017; Mohammed-Durosinlorun, 2019). Regional studies, such as one conducted in Bauchi State, Nigeria, report an infertility rate of 23.9% (Sulyman, 2019).

The causes of infertility are multifactorial and include male factors (11.1–59.0%), female factors (37.8%), a combination of both (40.0%), and unexplained (idiopathic) causes (11.1%) (Omidiji, 2019; Adelosoye, 2020). Oxidative stress has also been linked to infertility. Key contributors include free radicals such as superoxide anions, hydroxyl radicals, and

hydroperoxyl radicals. Hydrogen peroxide, although non-radical, also plays a physiologically significant role (Ikwuka, 2023b).

Research consistently shows that individuals facing infertility are more susceptible to anxiety and depression than fertile couples, significantly impacting their quality of life (Maroufizadeh, 2018). Depression and anxiety symptoms have been observed in approximately 40% of infertile women and between 4.9–38.0% of infertile men (Yang, 2017; Cusatis, 2019). For example, in Poland, 35.4% of infertile individuals reported depression and 19.5% anxiety, while in Nigeria, the prevalence of depression was 42.9% among infertile women in the South and 32% in Ekiti State, South-West Nigeria (Sulyman, 2019; Ojo, 2017). Crawford (2017) further reported that repeated failure in infertility treatment exacerbates depression and anxiety, which can profoundly impair overall well-being.

Quality of Life (QoL) is a multidimensional construct that reflects individuals' perception of their physical, psychological, social, and environmental health in relation to their personal goals and cultural context (Maj, 2020). Studies suggest that individuals with infertility often score higher in physical domains than in psychological ones, unless pain—a symptom of infertility—is severe and unmanaged, which can lower scores across all domains (Yela, 2020). Prolonged treatment failure also negatively impacts social and psychological domains (Sarafraz, 2020). Globally, low QoL has been reported among infertile individuals, especially women, those with less education, younger individuals, and those with idiopathic infertility. Shahraki (2019) found that poor sexual satisfaction significantly affects the social health of infertile individuals, thereby reducing their QoL. Psychological issues, particularly depression, remain the most significant contributors to poor QoL in this population (Sidra, 2019). The psychological burden is often disproportionately higher among women, especially in cultures where societal stigma against female infertility persists (Karaca, 2016; Cusatis, 2019).

Infertility treatment can be financially burdensome, emotionally challenging, and time-

intensive, often neglecting the broader psychosocial needs of patients. Failure to address the full spectrum of health—physical, mental, social, and environmental—may lead patients to discontinue treatment prematurely. It is thus critical for healthcare providers to assess the QoL of patients before and during infertility treatment. Nurses and midwives, in particular, can play an essential role in delivering comprehensive, patient-centred care throughout the treatment journey.

MSDs are chronic and interrelated conditions that contribute significantly to healthcare costs and mortality. Innovative treatment approaches, such as combining HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors, SGLT-2 inhibitors, and angiotensin II receptor blockers (A2RB), have shown clinical effectiveness in improving the metabolic function of key organs (Ikwuka, 2024; Ikwuka, 2017b; Ikwuka, 2018a; Ikwuka, 2018b; Ikwuka, 2021; Virstyuk, 2017b; Virstyuk, 2018b; Virstyuk, 2018c). Additionally, GLP-1 receptor agonists like liraglutide have been shown to improve the clinical outcomes in patients with type 2 diabetes and hypertension (Ikwuka, 2019b).

Most research on the quality of life of infertile individuals originates from Asia and North America, with limited data available from Nigeria. Where studies exist, they often focus exclusively on one gender (Oduşina, 2020). Expanding this area of research in Nigeria will not only deepen understanding of how infertility affects individuals' health, but also support clinicians in tailoring care strategies to address their physical, psychological, social, and environmental needs. Moreover, it will offer valuable comparative insights between populations in Nigeria and those in more developed contexts.

Thus, this study aims to assess the quality of life in individuals with infertility attending the fertility clinic at University College Hospital (UCH), Ibadan, Oyo State, South-West Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

Study Setting

This research was conducted at the University College Hospital (UCH), located in Ibadan

North Local Government Area (LGA) of Oyo State, in South-Western Nigeria. Ibadan North LGA spans an area of 132,500 square kilometres with a population density of approximately 2,626 people per square kilometre. Based on a 3.2% annual growth rate since the 2006 national census, the population was estimated at 347,998 in 2010.

UCH is Nigeria's foremost tertiary health institution, known for its excellence in medical training, service delivery, and research. Physical construction commenced in 1953, and the hospital was officially inaugurated on 20th November 1957. Initially operating with 500 beds, UCH has since expanded to 1,000 beds and 163 examination couches, maintaining occupancy rates between 55% and 60%. It houses around 65 departments, including the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, which consists of five specialist units: the Assisted Conception Unit (ACU), Fertility Research and Endocrinology Unit (FREU), Feto-Maternal Medicine Unit (FMMU), Genito-Urinary Unit (GUU), and Gynae-Oncology Unit (GOU).

Study Design

This study utilized a cross-sectional descriptive design.

Study Population

The study population constituted of individuals with infertility who attended gynecology clinics at UCH, Ibadan irrespective of their age, tribe, educational status, parity, or religion.

Sample Size

The sample size was calculated using Taro Yamane's 1967 formula which is as follows (Yamane, 1967):

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} \quad (1)$$

Where:

n = desired sample size for a finite population

N = population size = 770

e = level of precision desired or margin of sampling error = 0.05

Sample size, n = 263

Inclusion Criteria

- Individuals with infertility attending Gynecology Clinics at UCH, Ibadan within the period of this study for reasons connected with infertility
- Individuals with infertility attending Gynecology Clinics at UCH, Ibadan within the period of this study, who do not have other existing psychological problems such as depression, anxiety disorders

Exclusion Criteria

- All individuals attending Gynecology Clinics at UCH, Ibadan within the period of this study for other reasons which are not infertility
- Individuals with infertility attending Gynecology Clinics at UCH, Ibadan within the period of this study, who have other existing psychological problems such as depression, anxiety disorders

Sampling Technique

A simple random sampling technique was used to select respondents for this study. Patients were stratified into their clinic days. There are three (3) clinic days - Mondays, Tuesdays, and Thursdays. 'Yes' or 'No' was written in pieces of paper and was put in masked brown envelopes. On each clinic day, the masked ballots were taken to the clinic for the consenting respondents that were in the clinic for infertility reasons and not for other gynecological reasons, to pick from. Those that picked 'Yes' were recruited for the study to avoid bias and they were asked if they had filled the questionnaire before. The questionnaires were given to them to fill. It was ensured that the respondents filled only one questionnaire and not more than one.

Sampling Instrument

This study employed a modified version of the WHOQoL-100 BREF questionnaire. The original WHOQoL-100, developed in 1998, includes 100 items covering six domains to assess general health-related quality of life

(WHOQoL, 1998). Due to its length and complexity, the shorter WHOQoL-100 BREF was developed and adopted in this study for practical use (WHOQoL, 2012). The questionnaire was divided into two sections. Section A gathered demographic data such as age, education, occupation, income, family structure, duration of infertility, and spouse's employment. Section B contained 26 questions drawn from the WHOQoL-100 BREF, measuring quality of life across physical, psychological, social, and environmental domains using a five-point Likert scale. Specifically:

- Physical health was assessed using items 3, 4, 10, 15, 16, 17, and 18.
- Psychological health: items 5, 6, 7, 11, 19, and 26.
- Social relationships: items 20, 21, and 23.
- Environmental domain: items 8, 9, 12, 13, 14, 22, 24, and 25.

Reliability and Validation of Study Instruments

The WHOQoL-100 BREF is a globally validated instrument, designed to evaluate individuals' quality of life across multiple domains. Its four primary sections include physical health (e.g., daily activity, fatigue, sleep quality, discomfort), psychological well-being (e.g., self-esteem, mood, cognition), social relationships (e.g., support systems, sexual health), and environmental factors (e.g., financial stability, access to care, home environment, and recreational opportunities). The questionnaire has undergone international validation across 20 centres in 18 countries. Related validation studies include Akpa (2018) in Nigeria, Ilic (2019) in Serbia, and Kalfoss (2021) in Norway. Internal consistency measured by Cronbach's alpha in these studies yielded strong reliability: Akpa (2018) reported $\alpha = 0.862$ (Cronbach) and $\alpha = 0.989$ (Polychoric), Ilic (2019) recorded $\alpha = 0.896$, and Kalfoss (2021) obtained $\alpha = 0.92$.

Data Collection

A consent letter was written and attached to the study questionnaire explaining the purpose of

the study and period that the study would elapse. Consent was obtained and the respondents' pressing issues concerning the study were answered. The data collection was from February 1st to April 30th, 2022, in order to ensure that all selected respondents participated in the study.

The respondents filled only one questionnaire which took about 10-15 minutes and handed over the completed questionnaire immediately after the questionnaires were filled. Data was collected by one of the researchers and two research assistants, who were recruited for the study. The research assistants were trained in two stages. In the first stage, the research assistants got used to the question items and how to break down the questions to respondents who were illiterates. In the second stage, the research assistants were taught how to administer and retrieve the questionnaires. The questionnaires were administered to the respondents on their clinic days and emphasis was made on respondents filling only one questionnaire, hence there was no duplication of data.

Data Analysis

All data collected were entered into a secure database and processed by a professional statistician. The WHOQoL-100 BREF scores were calculated following the transformation table provided by the WHO, with scores ranging from 0 to 100—higher scores indicating better quality of life. Mean domain scores were computed by averaging the item responses within each domain and multiplying by a factor of 4 to standardise against the original WHOQoL-100 scoring system. Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 21. Descriptive statistics such as means, frequencies, and percentages were used to summarise variables. Cross-tabulations explored associations between categorical variables. Inferential statistics included Kruskal-Wallis tests, Mann-Whitney U tests, and Pearson product-moment correlations. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$, while $p < 0.01$ was regarded as highly significant.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for the study was granted by the University College Hospital, Ibadan. A formal approval letter was submitted to the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all respondents. Data collection adhered to strict confidentiality and anonymity protocols, with responses stored in a password-protected digital database. As part of ethical engagement, participants and healthcare

professionals received general health education concerning quality of life in individuals experiencing infertility.

Results and Discussion

Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to assess the research's questions and hypotheses. The results are presented under the following headings:

Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 1. Distribution of Age, Tribe and Gender of Respondents

Socio-demographic characteristics		Respondents	
Variable	Labels	N	%
Age group (mean 37.6±6.62)	25-34 years	96	36.5
	35-44 years	127	48.3
	45-54 years	37	14.1
	55-64 years	3	1.1
Tribe	Yoruba	205	77.9
	Hausa	6	2.3
	Igbo	34	12.9
	Fulani	3	1.1
	Others	15	5.7
Gender	Female	184	70.0
	Male	79	30.0

Table 1 shows that most of the respondents 96(36.5%) were between 25-34 years, 127(48.3%) were between 35-44 years, 37(14.1%) were between 45-54 years, and 3(1.1%) are between 55-64 years with the overall mean age and standard deviation of 37±6.62.

Majority of the respondents 205(77.9%) were Yoruba, 6(2.3%) were Hausa, 34(12.9%) were Igbo, 3(1.1%) were Fulani and 15(5.7%) were from other tribes. 184(70.0%) were females and 79(30.0%) were males.

Table 2. Distribution of Family Type and Duration of Infertility among the Respondents

Socio-demographic characteristics		Respondents	
Variable	Labels	N	%
Family type	Monogamous	202	76.8
	Polygamous	61	23.2
Duration of infertility	1-5 years	151	57.4
	6-10 years	76	28.9
	11-15 years	17	6.5
	>15 years	19	7.2

Table 2 shows that 202(76.8%) were monogamous and 61(23.2%) were polygamous. 151(57.4%) have been infertile for 1-5 years,

76(28.9%) for 6-10 years, 17(6.5%) for 11-15 years and 19(7.2%) for more than 15 years.

Table 3. Distribution of Spouse's Educational Status and Monthly Income of Family

Socio-demographic characteristics		Respondents	
Variable	Labels	N	%
Husband's educational status	PhD	12	4.6
	Master's degree	52	19.8
	Bachelor's degree	102	38.8
	HND	50	19.0
	OND	13	4.9
	NCE	9	3.4
Wife's educational status	SSCE	25	9.5
	PhD	3	1.1
	Master's degree	27	10.3
	Bachelor's degree	120	45.6
	HND	37	14.1
	OND	25	9.5
Monthly income of family	NCE	21	8.0
	SSCE	30	11.4
	<N10,000	6	2.3
	N10,000-49,000	43	16.3
	N50,000-100,000	88	33.5
	>N100,000	126	47.9

Table 3 shows that most spouses of the respondents were university graduates. Most families 126(47.9%) were on a monthly income of over N100,000.

Table 4. Distribution of Spouse's Occupation among the Respondents

Socio-demographic characteristics		Respondents	
Variable	Labels	N	%
Husband's occupation	Farmer	11	4.2
	Artisan	7	2.7
	Trading/Business	88	33.5
	Public servant	93	35.4
	Private sector	55	20.9
	Clergyman	9	3.4
Wife's occupation	Farmer	1	0.4
	Artisan	9	3.4
	Trading/Business	132	50.2
	Public servant	72	27.4
	Private sector	38	14.4
	Unemployed	9	3.4
	Students	2	0.8

Table 4 shows that majority of the husbands of the female respondents were public servants 93(35.4%), while most wives of the male respondents were traders or into business 132(50.2%).

Research Questions

Research Question 1: What is the physical health of individuals with infertility?

Table 5. Physical Health of Individuals with Infertility

S/No.	Variable	Labels	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)	Mean±SD
1	To what extent do you feel that physical pain prevents you from doing what you need to do?	An extreme amount	4	1.5	3.528±1.07
		Very much	46	17.5	
		A moderate amount	82	31.2	
		A little	69	26.2	

		Not at all	62	23.6	
2	How much do you need any medical treatment to function in your daily life?	Not at all	66	25.1	2.650±1.21
		A little	44	16.7	
		A moderate amount	81	30.8	
		Very much	60	22.8	
		An extreme amount	12	4.6	
3	Do you have enough energy for everyday life?	Not at all	1	0.4	3.577±0.96
		A little	38	14.4	
		Moderately	81	30.8	
		Mostly	94	35.7	
		Completely	49	18.6	
4	How well are you able to get around?	Very poor	3	1.1	3.730±0.77
		Poor	15	5.7	
		Neither poor nor good	61	23.2	
		Good	155	58.9	
		Very good	29	11.0	
5	How satisfied are you with your sleep?	Very dissatisfied	16	6.1	2.946±0.94
		Dissatisfied	65	24.7	
		Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	111	42.2	
		Satisfied	59	22.4	
		Very satisfied	12	4.6	
6	How satisfied are you with your ability to perform your daily life's activities?	Very dissatisfied	1	0.4	3.566±0.97
		Dissatisfied	39	14.8	
		Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	82	31.2	
		Satisfied	92	35.0	
		Very satisfied	49	18.6	
7	How satisfied are you with your capacity for work?	Very dissatisfied	1	0.4	3.574±0.97
		Dissatisfied	39	14.8	
		Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	81	30.8	
		Satisfied	92	35.0	
		Very satisfied	50	19.0	

Note: This table is based on the questionnaire designed by Harris, (2018)

Table 5 reveals the physical health of individuals with infertility. 31.2% individuals with infertility were moderately prevented by physical pain from doing what they need to do. 23.6% individuals with infertility were not at all prevented by physical pain from doing what they need to do. Only 14.4% of the individuals with infertility did not have enough energy for

everyday life. It was observed that the physical health of individuals with infertility in terms of being able to get around seems to be on the positive or good form as 58.9% individuals with infertility were well able to get around. Only 14.8% of individuals with infertility were dissatisfied with their ability to perform their daily life's activities.

Table 6. Overall Physical Health of Individuals with Infertility

Variable	Labels	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)	Mean	Std. Dev.	Median	Min	Max
Overall physical health of individuals with infertility	Inadequate	45	17.1	2.495	0.207	2.428	2.00	2.71
	Marginal	175	66.5	3.391	0.305	3.428	2.86	3.86
	Adequate	43	16.3	4.186	0.141	4.142	4.00	4.43
Total		263	100	3.367	0.559	3.428	2.00	4.43

Note: Inadequate: score \leq (overall mean-SD); Marginal: score $>$ (overall mean-SD) and $<$ (overall mean+SD); Adequate: score \geq (overall mean+SD)

Table 6 shows the overall physical health of individuals with infertility. The responses from the respondents on physical health were scored and summed together, such that the higher the score, the more physically healthy the individual, with the overall physically healthy scores as follows (mean=3.367, SD=0.559, median=3.428, min=2.00, max= 4.43). Individuals with infertility that scored between minimum score (2.00) and overall mean score-SD (2.495-0.207) were grouped as having inadequate physical health. Individuals that scored between overall mean score-SD (2.495-0.207) and overall mean score+SD (2.495+0.207) were grouped as having marginal

physical health, while individuals that scored \geq overall mean+SD (2.495+0.207) were grouped as having adequate physical health.

Table 6 also shows that out of 263 individuals with infertility, 17.1% with mean (2.495) and standard deviation (0.207) were having inadequate physical health, 66.5% with mean (3.391) and standard deviation (0.305) were marginally physically healthy, while 16.3% with mean (4.186) and standard deviation (0.141) were adequately physically healthy.

Research Question 2: What is the psychological health of individuals with infertility?

Table 7. Psychological Health of Individuals with Infertility

S/No.	Variable	Labels	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)	Mean \pm SD
1	How much do you enjoy life?	An extreme amount	23	8.7	3.273 \pm 0.88
		Very much	75	28.5	
		A moderate amount	120	45.6	
		A little	41	15.6	
		Not at all	4	1.5	
2	To what extent do you feel your life to be meaningful?	Not at all	1	0.4	3.654 \pm 0.86
		A little	25	9.5	
		A moderate amount	79	30.0	
		Very much	117	44.5	
		An extreme amount	41	15.6	
3	How well are you able to concentrate?	Not at all	2	0.8	3.330 \pm 0.88
		A little	46	17.5	
		A moderate amount	99	37.6	
		Very much	95	36.1	
		Extremely	21	8.0	
4	Are you able to accept your body's appearance?	Not at all	11	4.2	3.642 \pm 1.09
		A little	28	10.6	
		Moderately	72	27.4	
		Mostly	85	32.3	
		Completely	67	25.5	
5	How satisfied are you with yourself?	Very dissatisfied	11	4.2	3.616 \pm 1.09
		Dissatisfied	29	11.0	
		Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	75	28.5	
		Satisfied	83	31.6	
		Very satisfied	65	24.7	

Note: This table is based on the questionnaire designed by Israni, (2024).

Table 7 shows the psychological health of individuals with infertility. Most of the individuals with infertility were having good psychological health. 44.5% felt very much that their life was meaningful, and 15.6% felt

extremely much that their life was meaningful. 57.8% were either mostly or completely accepted their body's appearance, and 56.3% were either satisfied or very satisfied with themselves.

Table 8. Overall Psychological Health of Individuals with Infertility

Variable	Labels	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)	Mean	Std. Dev.	Median	Min	Max
Overall psychological health of individuals with infertility	Inadequate	38	14.4	2.321	0.252	2.40	1.80	2.60
	Marginal	186	70.7	3.519	0.451	3.60	2.80	4.20
	Adequate	39	14.8	4.579	0.228	4.40	4.40	5.00
Total		263	100	3.503	0.731	3.60	1.80	5.00

Note: Inadequate: score \leq (overall mean-SD); Marginal: score $>$ (overall mean-SD) and $<$ (overall mean+SD); Adequate: score \geq (overall mean+SD)

Table 8 shows the overall psychological health of individuals with infertility. The table reveals that 14.4% with mean (2.321) and standard deviation (0.252) of individuals with infertility were inadequately psychologically healthy. 70.7% with mean (3.519) and standard deviation (0.451) were marginally psychologically healthy,

and 14.8% with mean (4.579) and standard deviation (0.228) were having adequate psychological health.

Research Question 3: What is the social health of individuals with infertility?

Table 9. Social Health of Individuals with Infertility

S/No.	Variable	Labels	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)	Mean±SD
1	How satisfied are you with your personal relationships?	Very dissatisfied	3	1.1	3.285±0.86
		Dissatisfied	39	14.8	
		Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	124	47.1	
		Satisfied	74	28.1	
		Very satisfied	23	8.7	
2	How satisfied are you with your sex life?	Very dissatisfied	4	1.5	3.281±0.87
		Dissatisfied	38	14.4	
		Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	124	47.1	
		Satisfied	74	28.1	
		Very satisfied	23	8.7	
3	How satisfied are you with the support you get from your family and friends?	Very dissatisfied	24	9.1	2.965±1.06
		Dissatisfied	60	22.8	
		Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	102	38.8	
		Satisfied	55	20.9	
		Very satisfied	22	8.4	

Table 9 shows the social health of individuals with infertility. It was observed that 47.1% were neither satisfied nor dissatisfied with their personal relationships, and 28.1% were satisfied

with their personal relationships. 36.8% were either satisfied or very satisfied with their sex life. 29.3% were either satisfied or very satisfied with the support they get from their friends.

Table 10. Overall Social Health of Individuals with Infertility

Variable	Labels	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)	Mean	Std. Dev.	Median	Min	Max
Overall social health of individuals with infertility	Inadequate	47	17.9	2.070	0.33	2.333	1.00	2.33
	Marginal	169	64.3	3.159	0.36	3.000	2.67	3.67
	Adequate	47	17.9	4.347	0.38	4.333	4.00	5.00
Total		263	100	3.177	0.77	3.000	1.00	5.00

Note: Inadequate: score \leq (overall mean-SD); Marginal: score $>$ (overall mean-SD) and $<$ (overall mean+SD); Adequate: score \geq (overall mean+SD)

Table 10 shows the overall social health of individuals with infertility. The table reveals that 17.9% with mean (2.070) and standard deviation (0.33) were inadequately socially healthy. 64.3% with mean (3.159) and standard deviation (0.36) were marginally socially healthy, and 17.9% with

mean (4.347) and standard deviation (0.38) were having adequate social health.

Research Question 4: What is the environmental health of individuals with infertility?

Table 11. Environmental Health of Individuals with Infertility

S/No.	Variable	Labels	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)	Mean±SD
1	How safe do you feel within your environment in your daily life?	Not at all	1	0.4	3.475±0.82
		A little	24	9.1	
		A moderate amount	116	44.1	
		Very much	93	35.4	
		Extremely	29	11.0	
2	How healthy is your physical environment?	A little	17	6.5	3.619±0.80
		A moderate amount	102	38.8	
		Very much	108	41.1	
		Extremely	36	13.7	
3	Do you have enough money to meet your needs?	Not at all	15	5.7	2.996±0.98
		A little	65	24.7	
		Moderately	107	40.7	
		Mostly	58	22.1	
		Completely	18	6.8	
4	How available to you is the information that you need in your day-to-day life?	Not at all	2	0.8	3.193±0.85
		A little	54	20.5	
		Moderately	114	43.3	
		Mostly	77	29.3	
		Completely	16	6.1	
5	To what extent do you have the opportunity for leisure activities?	Not at all	15	5.7	2.950±0.93
		A little	65	24.7	
		Moderately	113	43.0	
		Mostly	58	22.1	
		Completely	12	4.6	
6	How satisfied are you with the conditions of your living place?	Dissatisfied	20	7.6	3.612±0.81
		Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	97	36.9	
		Satisfied	111	42.2	
		Very satisfied	35	13.3	
7	How satisfied are you with your access to health services?	Very dissatisfied	5	1.9	3.517±0.91
		Dissatisfied	34	12.9	
		Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	71	27.0	
		Satisfied	126	47.9	
		Very satisfied	27	10.3	

8	How satisfied are you with your transport services?	Very dissatisfied	3	1.1	3.714±0.78
		Dissatisfied	16	6.1	
		Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	62	23.6	
		Satisfied	154	58.6	
		Very satisfied	28	10.6	

Table 11 shows the environmental health of individuals with infertility. 44.1% were to a moderately amount felt safe in their daily life. 54.8% were either very much or extremely agreed that their physical environment was

healthy. 43.3% moderately had access to the information they needed in their day-to-day life. 55.5% were either satisfied or very satisfied with the conditions of their living place. 58.6% were satisfied with their transport services.

Table 12. Overall environmental health of individuals with infertility

Variable	Labels	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)	Mean	Std. Dev.	Median	Min	Max
Overall environmental health of individuals with infertility	Inadequate	45	17.1	2.519	0.221	2.500	1.88	2.75
	Marginal	171	65.0	3.386	0.291	3.375	2.88	3.88
	Adequate	47	17.9	4.210	0.243	4.125	4.00	4.88
Total		263	100	3.385	0.569	3.375	1.88	4.88

Note: Inadequate: score \leq (overall mean-SD); Marginal: score $>$ (overall mean-SD) and $<$ (overall mean+SD); Adequate: score \geq (overall mean+SD)

Table 12 shows the overall environmental health of individuals with infertility. The table shows that 17.1% were inadequately environmentally

healthy, 65.0% were marginally environmentally healthy, and 17.9% were having adequate environmental health.

Table 13. Overall Quality of Life (QoL) in Individuals with Infertility

Variable	Labels	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)	Mean	Std. Dev.	Median	Min	Max
Overall quality of life in individuals with infertility	Inadequate	44	16.7	2.510	0.191	2.571	2.06	2.75
	Marginal	182	69.2	3.384	0.319	3.384	2.80	3.91
	Adequate	37	14.1	4.237	0.200	4.198	3.94	4.75
Total		263	100	3.358	0.559	3.363	2.06	4.75

Note: Inadequate: score \leq (overall mean-SD); Marginal: score $>$ (overall mean-SD) and $<$ (overall mean+SD); Adequate: score \geq (overall mean+SD)

The scores of the respondents on physical, psychological, social, and environmental health were summed together to represent the individual's quality of life scores, such that the higher the score, the better the individual's quality of life, with the overall quality of life as follows (mean=3.358, SD=0.559, median=3.363, min=2.06, max= 4.75). All individuals that scored between (minimum score) and (overall mean score-SD) were grouped as having inadequate quality of life.

Individuals that scored between (overall mean score-SD) and (overall mean score+SD) were grouped as having marginal quality of life, while individuals that scored \geq (overall mean+SD) were grouped as having adequate quality of life.

Table 13 shows that 16.7% with mean (2.510) and standard deviation (0.191) were having inadequate quality of life, 69.2% with mean (3.384) and standard deviation (0.319) were having marginal quality of life, and 14.1% with

mean (4.237) and standard deviation (0.200) were having adequate quality of life.

Research Question 5: What are the predictors of quality of life in individuals with infertility?

Table 14. Socio-Demographic Characteristics and Quality of Life (QoL) Scores among the Respondents

Socio-demographic characteristics		Quality of Life		
Variable	Labels	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
Age group	25-34 years	96	3.239	0.558
	35-44 years	127	3.404	0.574
	45-54 years	37	3.513	0.462
	55-64 years	3	3.322	0.488
Tribe	Yoruba	205	3.386	0.534
	Hausa	6	3.264	0.763
	Igbo	34	3.190	0.606
	Fulani	3	3.688	0.585
	Other	15	3.330	0.671
Gender	Male	79	3.359	0.592
	Female	184	3.357	0.545
Family Type	Monogamous	202	3.352	0.574
	Polygamous	61	3.378	0.510
Duration of Infertility	1-5 years	151	3.397	0.537
	6-10 years	76	3.184	0.551
	11-15 years	17	3.627	0.624
	>15 years	19	3.504	0.544
Husband's educational status	PhD	12	2.765	0.682
	Master's degree	52	3.564	0.486
	Bachelor's degree	102	3.368	0.519
	HND	50	3.332	0.636
	OND	13	3.232	0.603
	NCE	9	3.286	0.290
	SSCE	25	3.317	0.491
Wife's educational status	PhD	3	3.501	0.198
	Master's degree	27	3.501	0.475
	Bachelor's degree	120	3.380	0.614
	HND	37	3.434	0.499
	OND	25	3.329	0.622
	NCE	21	3.087	0.508
Husband's occupation	Farmer	11	3.189	0.731
	Artisan	7	3.086	0.391
	Trading/business	88	3.312	0.574
	Public servant	93	3.432	0.482
	Private sector	55	3.361	0.639
	Clergyman	9	3.441	0.475
Wife's occupation	Farmer	1	4.440	0.000
	Artisan	9	3.468	0.776
	Trading/business	132	3.343	0.550
	Public servant	72	3.452	0.517
	Private sector	38	3.342	0.544
	Unemployed	9	2.710	0.439
	Student	2	3.125	0.088
Monthly income	< N10,000	6	3.781	0.322
	N10,000–49,000	43	3.309	0.531
	N50,000–100,000	88	3.330	0.590
	>N100,000	126	3.374	0.550

Table 15. Association between Socio-Demographic Characteristics and Quality of Life in Individuals with Infertility (using Kruskal-Wallis and Mann-Whitney Test Analyses)

	Physical Health Chi-square, <i>df</i> , <i>p</i> -value	Psychological Health Chi-square, <i>df</i> , <i>p</i> - value	Social Health Chi-square, <i>df</i> , <i>p</i> -value	Environmental Health Chi-square, <i>df</i> , <i>p</i> - value	Overall Quality of Life Chi-square, <i>df</i> , <i>p</i> -value
Age group	Kruskal-Wallis, X = 4.396 <i>df</i> = 3 <i>p</i> -value = 0.222	Kruskal-Wallis, X = 12.355 <i>df</i> = 3 <i>p</i> -value = 0.006***	Kruskal-Wallis, X = 2.221 <i>df</i> = 3 <i>p</i> -value = 0.528	Kruskal-Wallis, X = 12.455 <i>df</i> = 3 <i>p</i> -value = 0.006	Kruskal-Wallis, X = 10.199 <i>df</i> = 3 <i>p</i>-value = 0.017
Tribe	X = 8.860 <i>df</i> = 4 <i>p</i> -value = 0.065	X = 5.526 <i>df</i> = 4 <i>p</i> -value = 0.237	X = 2.366 <i>df</i> = 4 <i>p</i> -value = 0.669	X = 1.349 <i>df</i> = 4 <i>p</i> -value = 0.853	X = 4.438 <i>df</i> = 4 <i>p</i> -value = 0.350
Gender	Mann-Whitney, U = 7221.500 <i>p</i> -value = 0.934	Mann-Whitney, U = 7094.500 <i>p</i> -value = 0.758	Mann-Whitney, U = 7130.500 <i>p</i> -value = 0.806	Mann-Whitney, U = 7038.000 <i>p</i> -value = 0.683	Mann-Whitney, U = 7162.500 <i>p</i> -value = 0.852
Family type	U = 6138.500 <i>p</i> -value = 0.965	U = 6087.500 <i>p</i> -value = 0.887	U = 5942.000 <i>p</i> -value = 0.671	U = 6139.000 <i>p</i> -value = 0.966	U = 6009.500 <i>p</i> -value = 0.771
Duration of infertility	X = 8.375 <i>df</i> = 3 <i>p</i> -value = 0.039	X = 14.141 <i>df</i> = 3 <i>p</i> -value = 0.003	X = 10.539 <i>df</i> = 3 <i>p</i> -value = 0.014	X = 10.340 <i>df</i> = 3 <i>p</i> -value = 0.016	X = 13.138 <i>df</i> = 3 <i>p</i>-value = 0.004
Husband's educational status	X = 10.657 <i>df</i> = 6 <i>p</i> -value = 0.100	X = 11.529 <i>df</i> = 6 <i>p</i> -value = 0.073	X = 23.582 <i>df</i> = 6 <i>p</i> -value = 0.001	X = 20.270 <i>df</i> = 6 <i>p</i> -value = 0.002	X = 16.715 <i>df</i> = 6 <i>p</i>-value = 0.010
Wife's educational status	X = 4.647 <i>df</i> = 6 <i>p</i> -value = 0.590	X = 6.203 <i>df</i> = 6 <i>p</i> -value = 0.401	X = 11.709 <i>df</i> = 6 <i>p</i> -value = 0.069	X = 16.640 <i>df</i> = 6 <i>p</i> -value = 0.011	X = 9.689 <i>df</i> = 6 <i>p</i> -value = 0.138
Husband's occupation	X = 7.557 <i>df</i> = 5 <i>p</i> -value = 0.182	X = 3.768 <i>df</i> = 5 <i>p</i> -value = 0.583	X = 6.183 <i>df</i> = 5 <i>p</i> -value = 0.289	X = 11.026 <i>df</i> = 5 <i>p</i> -value = 0.051	X = 5.913 <i>df</i> = 5 <i>p</i> -value = 0.315
Wife's occupation	X = 16.974 <i>df</i> = 6 <i>p</i> -value = 0.009	X = 18.082 <i>df</i> = 6 <i>p</i> -value = 0.006	X = 10.499 <i>df</i> = 6 <i>p</i> -value = 0.105	X = 18.783 <i>df</i> = 6 <i>p</i> -value = 0.005	X = 18.413 <i>df</i> = 6 <i>p</i>-value = 0.005
Monthly income	X = 2.876 <i>df</i> = 3 <i>p</i> -value = 0.411	X = 3.485 <i>df</i> = 3 <i>p</i> -value = 0.323	X = 8.759 <i>df</i> = 3 <i>p</i> -value = 0.033	X = 7.726 <i>df</i> = 3 <i>p</i> -value = 0.052	X = 4.895 <i>df</i> = 3 <i>p</i> -value = 0.180

Table 15 revealed that age group has a statistically significant association with the quality of life (Kruskal-Wallis coefficient=10.199, *df*=3, *p*=0.017), where the quality of life was lowest among the youngest age group 25-34 years: QoL=3.239±0.558 (see Table 16).

Table 15 also shows that the duration of infertility has a statistically significant association with the quality of life (Kruskal-Wallis coefficient=13.138, *df*=3, *p*=0.004), where

individuals with longer duration of infertility were having higher quality of life - 1-5 years: QoL=3.397±0.537, 6-10 years: QoL=3.184±0.551, 11-15 years: QoL=3.627±0.624, >15years: QoL=3.504±0.544 (see Table 16).

In addition, Table 15 also showed that other socio-demographic characteristics that had statistically significant association with the quality of life were husband's educational status and wife's occupation (see also Table 16).

Table 16. Multivariate Logistic Regression for Relationships between Socio-Demographic Characteristics and Overall Quality of Life in Individuals with Infertility (1st: Comparing Individuals with Inadequate Quality of Life with Those that Have Adequate Quality of Life)

Individuals with inadequate quality of life		Odds Ratio (OR)	Significance	95% Confidence Interval (CI)	
				Lower limit	Upper limit
Age group	25-34 years	0.417	0.594	0.017	10.372
	35-44 years	1.590	0.747	0.095	26.729
	45-54 years	1.000	---	---	---
	55-64 years	---	---	---	---
Duration of infertility	1-5 years	8.501	0.202	0.317	227.778
	6-10 years	52.819***	0.018	1.962	1422.297
	11-15 years	6.975	0.319	0.153	318.349
	>15 years	1	---	---	---
Husband's educational status	PhD	4688	0.976	0.000	0.000
	Master's degree	12.652	0.133	0.463	345.793
	Bachelor's degree	88.163***	0.006	3.573	2173.800
	HND	14.265	0.087	0.682	298.391
	OND	278.719	0.071	0.573	21739.703
	NCE	3984	0.957	0.000	0.000
	SSCE	---	---	---	---
Wife's occupation	Farmer	3.243E+24	0.998	0.000	---
	Artisan	6.748E+17	0.998	0.000	---
	Trading/business	6.196E+15	0.998	0.000	---
	Public servant	1.970E+16	0.998	0.000	---
	Private sector	3.442E+15	0.998	0.000	---
	Unemployed	---	---	---	---
	Student	---	---	---	---

Note: *** significant at $p \leq 0.05$

Table 16 presents the multivariate logistic regression analysis for predicting variables affecting the quality of life in individuals with infertility (firstly, comparing individuals with infertility having inadequate quality of life with those having adequate quality of life). Table 16 shows that there were statistically significant associations between variables such as “duration of infertility” (OR: 6-10 years=52.819, CI=1.962-1422.297, $p=0.018$) and “husband’s educational status” (OR: Bachelor’s

degree=88.163, CI=3.573-2173.800, $p=0.006$) with the quality of life in individuals with infertility. Table 16 also shows that individuals with infertility that have inadequate quality of life are more likely to be found among those whose duration of infertility were between 6-10 years compared to those with adequate quality of life (OR=52.819), and that more bachelor’s degree holders are more likely to be having inadequate quality of life compared to those with adequate quality of life (OR=88.163).

Table 17. Multivariate Logistic Regression for Relationships between Socio-Demographic Characteristics and Overall Quality of Life in Individuals with Infertility (2nd: Comparing Individuals with Marginal Quality of Life with Those that Have Adequate Quality of Life)

Individuals with marginal quality of life		Odds Ratio (OR)	Significance	95% Confidence Interval (CI)	
				Lower limit	Upper limit
Age group	25-34 years	12925E+4	0.999	0.000	---
	35-44 years	20021E+4	0.999	0.000	---
	45-54 years	11947E+4	0.999	0.000	---
	55-64 years	---	---	---	---
Duration of infertility	1-5 years	8.992***	0.042	1.081	74.812
	6-10 years	14.273***	0.013	1.759	115.826
	11-15 years	2.877	0.381	0.271	30.571

	>15 years	1.000	---	---	---
Husband's educational status	PhD	94.79	0.981	0.000	0.000
	Master's degree	4.712	0.220	0.396	56.111
	Bachelor's degree	25.261***	0.015	1.853	344.393
	HND	6.322	0.145	0.531	75.291
	OND	20.450	0.121	0.449	930.431
	NCE	6.196E10	0.952	0.000	0.000
	SSCE	1	---	---	---
Wife's occupation	Farmer	1.597E+18	0.999	0.000	---
	Artisan	556171E+4	0.999	0.000	---
	Trading/business	576187E+3	0.999	0.000	---
	Public servant	365351E+3	0.999	0.000	---
	Private sector	444006E+2	0.999	0.000	---
	Unemployed	1.674	1.000	0.000	---
	Student	1	---	---	---

Note: *** significant at $p \leq 0.05$

Table 17 shows the multivariate logistic regression analysis for predicting variables affecting the quality of life in individuals with infertility (secondly, comparing individuals with infertility having marginal quality of life with those having adequate quality of life). Table 17 reveals that individuals with infertility with

duration 1-5 years (OR=8.992), 6-10 years (OR=14.273), and having a husband with a bachelor's degree (OR=25.261) were more likely to be found among those with marginal quality of life compared to those with adequate quality of life.

Table 18. Distribution of Individual's Quality of Life by Duration of Infertility and Husband's Educational Status

Socio-demographic characteristics		Quality of life in individuals with infertility		
		Inadequate QoL	Marginal QoL	Adequate QoL
Variable	Labels			
Duration of infertility	1-5 years	22	108	21
	6-10 years	19	50	7
	11-15 years	2	9	6
	>15 years	1	15	3
Husband's educational status	PhD	7	5	0
	Master's degree	3	37	12
	Bachelor's degree	14	75	13
	HND	11	31	8
	OND	5	7	1
	NCE	1	8	0
	SSCE	3	19	3

Tests of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no statistically significant relationship between socio-

demographic characteristics (age, duration of infertility, family type) and quality of life.

Table 19. Kruskal-Wallis Test Showing Relationships between Socio-Demographic Characteristics (Age, Duration of Infertility) and Quality of Life

Socio-demographic characteristics		Respondents		Kruskal-Wallis Test Analysis for Overall Quality of Life (QoL) scores					
Variable	Labels	N	%	Mean±SD	Rank mean	Chi-square	df	p-value	Remark
Age group	25-34 years	96	36.5	3.239±0.558	113.72	10.199	3	0.017	Significant
	35-44 years	127	48.3	3.404±0.574	139.00				
	45-54 years	37	14.1	3.513±0.462	155.64				
	55-64 years		1.1	3.322±0.559	129.00				
Duration of infertility	1-5 years	151	57.4	3.397±0.537	137.11	13.138	3	0.004	Significant
	6-10 years	76	28.9	3.184±0.551	108.68				
	11-15 years	17	6.5	3.627±0.624	169.29				
	>15 years		7.2	3.504±0.544	151.32				

Table 19 shows the results of Kruskal-Wallis test which indicated that the individual's age group (Chi-square=10.199, $df=3$, p -value=0.017), and duration of infertility (Chi-square=13.138, $df=3$,

p -value=0.004) had statistically significant relationships with the quality of life in individuals with infertility.

Table 20. Mann-Whitney Test Showing Relationship between Family Type and the Quality of Life in Individuals with Infertility

Respondents				Mann-Whitney Test for Overall Quality of Life (QoL) scores by sex				
Variable	Labels	N	%	Mean±SD	Rank mean	Mann-Whitney, U	p-value	Remark
Family type	Monogamous	202	76.8	3.352±0.574	131.25	6009.50	0.771	Not Significant
	Polygamous	61	23.2	3.378±0.510	134.48	---	---	

Table 20 shows that there was no statistically significant relationship between family type and the quality of life in individuals with infertility (Mann-Whitney, $U=6009.50$, p -value=0.771). Thus, there are only statistically significant relationships between age group and duration of infertility with the quality of life in individuals with infertility.

Hypothesis 1 is therefore rejected.

Hypothesis 2: There is no statistically significant association between physical health and psychological health of individuals with infertility

Table 21. Association between Physical Health and Psychological Health of Individuals with Infertility Using Pearson Product Moment Correlation

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	Pearson correlation coefficient (r)	p-value	Remark
Physical health	3.3677	0.559	263	0.665	0.001	Significant
Psychological health	3.5034	0.731				

Table 21 reveals the correlation between physical health and psychological health of individuals with infertility, showing that there is a significant

positive correlation between physical health and psychological health of individuals with infertility ($r=0.665$, $p=0.001$).

Table 22. Binomial Logistic Regression Analysis Showing Relationships between Physical Health and Psychological Health of Individuals with Infertility

Physical health (dependent variable)	Psychological health (independent variable)							Remark
	B	Wald	df	p-value	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% Confidence Interval (CI)		
						Lower limit	Upper limit	
Marginal physical health	2.887	42.153	1	0.000	17.937	7.504	42.878	Significant
Adequate physical health	4.376	61.968	1	0.000	79.511	26.746	236.373	Significant

Note: Using Inadequate physical health individuals as a reference category

Table 22 shows binomial logistic regression analysis which indicated that the psychological health of individuals with marginal physical health is 17.937 times significantly higher than that of individuals with inadequate physical health (OR=17.937, CI=7.504-42.878, $p=0.000$). Table 22 also reveals that the psychological health of individuals with adequate physical health is 79.511 times significantly higher than that of individuals with inadequate physical health (OR=79.511, CI=26.746-236.373,

$p=0.000$). Thus, there is a statistically significant association between physical health and psychological health of individuals with infertility.

Hypothesis 2 is therefore rejected.

Hypothesis 3: There is no statistically significant association between social health and environmental health of individuals with infertility.

Table 23. Association between Social Health and Environmental Health of Individuals with Infertility Using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	Pearson correlation coefficient (r)	p-value	Remark
Social health	3.1774	0.770	263	0.635	0.001	Significant
Environmental health	3.3850	0.569				

Table 23 shows the correlation analysis between social health and environmental health of individuals with infertility, which indicated that

there is a significant positive correlation between social health and environmental health of individuals with infertility ($r=0.635$, $p=0.001$).

Table 24. Binomial Logistic Regression Analysis Showing the Relationship between Social Health and Environmental Health of Individuals with Infertility

Social health (dependent variable)	Environmental health (independent variable)							Remark
	B	Wald	df	p-value	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% Confidence Interval (CI)		
						Lower Limit	Upper Limit	
Marginal social health	2.406	32.453	1	0.000	11.091	4.847	25.379	Significant
Adequate social health	4.717	62.418	1	0.000	111.846	34.706	360.448	Significant

Note: Using Inadequate social health group as a reference category

Table 24 shows the binomial logistic regression analysis which indicated that the environmental health of individual with marginal social health is 11.091 times more significantly higher than that of individuals with inadequate social health (OR=11.091, CI=4.847-25.379, $p=0.000$). Table 24 also shows that the environmental health of individuals with adequate social health is 111.846 times more significantly higher than that of individuals with inadequate social health (OR=111.846, CI=34.706-360.448, $p=0.000$).

Thus, there is a statistically significant association between social health and environmental health of individuals with infertility.

Hypothesis 3 is therefore rejected.

Hypothesis 4: There is no statistically significant association between the quality of life in women with infertility and the quality of life in men with infertility.

Table 25. Mann-Whitney Test Showing Relationship between the Quality of Life in Women with Infertility and the Quality of Life in Men with Infertility

Respondents				Mann-Whitney Test for Overall Quality of Life (QoL) scores by sex				
Variable	Labels	N	%	Mean±SD	Rank mean	Mann-Whitney, U	p-value	Remark
Gender	Female	184	70.0	3.357±0.545	131.43	10.199	0.852	Not significant
	Male	79	30.0	3.359±0.592	133.34			

Table 25 shows that the quality of life in women with infertility has no statistically significant association with the quality of life in men with infertility (Mann-Whitney, $U=10.199$, p -value=0.852).

Hypothesis 4 is therefore accepted.

Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents and Predictors of the Quality of Life (QoL)

This study included respondents from various ethnic backgrounds, both genders, and a range of educational levels, family structures, and durations of infertility, without significant age bias. This aligns with the findings of Aduloju (2017), whose research also incorporated diverse ethnicities, educational backgrounds, and infertility durations without age-related exclusions. A majority of respondents were of Yoruba ethnicity (77.9%), while a smaller proportion (12.9%) were Igbo, which is consistent with the sample distribution in Aduloju's (2017) study.

In this study, 70.0% of respondents were female and 30.0% were male, supporting Kiani's (2020) observation that infertility is predominantly

perceived as a female concern. This is further corroborated by Cavdar (2018), whose study reported that only 33.0% of respondents were male. Interestingly, gender was not a statistically significant predictor of QoL in the current research, with males scoring 3.359 and females 3.357—indicating virtually identical outcomes. This contradicts Grube (2019), who observed higher QoL among infertile men compared to women, but supports Cusatis (2019), who found that infertility reduces quality of life in both sexes equally.

The largest age group in this study was 35–44 years (48.3%), while only 1.1% of respondents were aged 55–64 years. Age emerged as a significant predictor of QoL. Among respondents under 35 years old (36.5%), lower QoL scores were observed, supporting Vaghar's (2019) claim that younger individuals tend to be less affected by their infertility. Conversely, older respondents exhibited higher QoL scores: 45–54 years (3.513), 35–44 years (3.404), and 25–34 years (3.239). These findings echo those of Cusatis (2019), who noted that as individuals with infertility age, they tend to develop coping mechanisms that improve their quality of life.

Regarding infertility duration, 57.4% of respondents had been infertile for 1–5 years, while 7.2% had experienced infertility for more than 15 years. The duration of infertility was found to be a significant predictor of QoL. Respondents with a history of infertility exceeding 15 years had a higher mean QoL score (3.504) compared to those with a duration of 1–5 years (3.397). This trend supports the conclusions of Cavdar (2018), who suggested that individuals become more accepting of their infertility over time, thus improving their overall well-being.

Educational attainment also played a role. Among male partners of infertile women, 38.8% held a bachelor's degree, while 45.6% of female partners of infertile men held the same qualification. The educational level of the husband was a significant QoL predictor; individuals whose partners held higher degrees reported higher QoL scores: Master's (3.564), Bachelor's (3.368), HND (3.332), OND (3.232), NCE (3.286), and SSCE (3.317). These findings are in agreement with Namdar (2017), who observed that individuals with higher education levels—especially those residing in urban areas with better access to information—tend to report a better quality of life.

Regarding income, 2.3% of respondents earned less than 10,000 naira per month, while 47.9% earned more than 100,000 naira. Interestingly, those in the lowest income bracket reported a higher QoL score (3.781) compared to their higher-earning counterparts (3.374). This finding supports Asazawa (2018), who identified income, education, age, and duration of infertility as key determinants of QoL among infertile individuals. However, it contrasts with the findings of Jahromi (2018), who reported a direct correlation between higher income and improved QoL, suggesting that the influence of income may vary by context or cultural setting.

Physical Health of Individuals with Infertility

This present study revealed that only 19.0% of individuals with infertility were prevented by physical pain (to an extreme amount and very much) from doing what they needed to do. This is in agreement with (Xiaoli, 2016) which

affirmed that individuals with infertility have positive physical quality of life because of their independent lifestyle. In this present study, 74.9% of the respondents needed medication to function in their daily life. This supports the findings of (Rooney, 2018), and (Johnson, 2021) that some of the drugs used in treating infertility have adverse effect on individuals with infertility which as a result influence their activities of daily living.

This present study also showed that only 27.0% of individuals with infertility were either satisfied or very satisfied with their sleep, meaning that about 73.0% were not really satisfied with their sleep. This finding agrees with the report of (Arc, 2021) which affirmed that the sleeping pattern of majority of individuals with infertility are distorted, hence their quality of life might be affected. Based on this present study, only 54.0% of the respondents were very satisfied or satisfied with their capacity for work. This agrees with (Asazawa, 2018) that fertility treatment is stressful. Hence, individuals with infertility find it difficult to combine fertility treatment with their work.

66.5% of individuals with infertility have marginal quality of physical health (3.391).

Psychological Health of Individuals with Infertility

In this present study, 98.5% of the respondents enjoy life to various degrees. 60.1% of individuals with infertility have good self-esteem. This is in contrast to a previous study which found that individuals with infertility are at risk of low self-esteem (Alimohamadi, 2020). Majority of individuals with infertility (81.7%) do not have challenges with concentration. This finding disagrees with a previous study which reported that most individuals with infertility have psychological challenges which in turn affect their cognition (Shahraki, 2019).

This present study showed that 85.2% of individuals with infertility accept their body's appearances. This corroborates the study conducted by (Bradley University, 2021) on body appearance of individuals with infertility where 93.0% of the respondents scored higher body image marks which shows that body image

is not a trivial issue in infertility. In this present study, 15.2% of individuals with infertility were very dissatisfied or dissatisfied with themselves. This is in contrast to a previous study which reported that infertility is associated with a negative feeling (Mohammed-Durosinlorun, 2019). However, the finding in this present study supports the report by (Royani, 2019) that despite the fact that infertility is associated with negative feelings, individuals with infertility prevent the negative feelings.

70.7% of individuals with infertility have marginal quality of psychological health (3.519).

Social Health of Individuals with Infertility

In this present study, only 36.8% were satisfied or very satisfied with their personal relationships, 47.1% were not sure, but 15.9% are quite sure that they are not satisfied with their personal relationships. This may occur as a result of inadequate knowledge about infertility and their personalities which made it difficult for them to cope with infertility as stated by (Kiani, 2020). 36.8% of individuals with infertility were either satisfied or very satisfied with their sex life, meaning that 63.2% were not really satisfied or not sure. This agrees with the findings of (Luk, 2018) which observed that because of the undue pressure on individuals with infertility, their sexual activity will become a routine and basically for conception thus leading to a dysfunctional sex. (Youseflu, 2020) buttressed that dysfunctional sex reduces the quality of life, can cause infertility, and prolong the duration of infertility. This is not good for an adequate quality of life.

Only 29.3% of individuals with infertility were either satisfied or very satisfied with the support they get from family and friends, while 70.7% were not satisfied or unsure. This may not encourage good quality of life. Social support is the strongest determinant of the quality of life (Song, 2021). Hence, individuals with infertility who have adequate social support from significant others have a higher quality of life compared to others who do not have social support. In addition, social support is difficult these days because of how the society is structured (Song, 2021). Another study is of the opinion that social support helps individuals

with infertility to seek for treatment, and adhere strictly to infertility treatment regimen (Rooney, 2018).

64.3% of individuals with infertility have marginal quality of social health (3.159).

Environmental Health of Individuals with Infertility

In this present study, 90.5% of the respondents felt safe within their environment in their daily lives. In this present study, 28.9% of the respondents have enough money to meet their needs, whereas 65.4% have little to moderate money, and 5.7% do not have money at all to meet their needs. This agrees with a study conducted on the need of finance for individuals with infertility (Strosberg, 2021), which showed that fertility treatment is expensive, and therefore there is a need to be financially capable in order to cater for the expenses of fertility treatment, as individuals with infertility that cannot afford fertility treatment may feel dejected thinking they are failures, hence leading to a poor quality of life.

41.8% of individuals with infertility were not satisfied or not sure with regards to access to health services. This agrees with the report of a study conducted by (Aregbeshola, 2019), which stated that the state of health services in developing countries such as Nigeria needs reviving, before it can cater for the needs of its citizens.

65.0% of individuals with infertility have marginal quality of environmental health (3.386).

In general, findings from this present study revealed that there is a significant positive correlation between physical health and psychological health of individuals with infertility ($r=0.665$, $p=0.001$), and a significant positive correlation between social health and environmental health of individuals with infertility ($r=0.635$, $p=0.001$). However, this present study found that the quality of life in individuals with infertility had no statistically significant relationship with gender (Mann-Whitney, $U=10.199$, $p\text{-value}=0.852$).

Some of the limitations of this present study include the fact that only few respondents were

able to express their minds and thoughts concerning their social health and environmental health on one-on-one basis. Majority of the respondents were shy about this. In addition, the female gender dominated the sample size because only few infertile men attend fertility clinics.

Prospects for further studies include the fact that similar studies should be conducted in other geopolitical zones. If possible, a nationwide survey should be carried out to establish the quality of life in individuals with infertility. Moreover, there is need for more qualitative studies – to be able to observe deeply the lifestyle of individuals with infertility, and intervention studies - to find a means through which the quality of life in individuals with infertility can be improved upon. Equal or nearly equal sample size numbers of both genders should be used in the next studies, in order to give a clearer picture of the quality of life in individuals with infertility.

Conclusion

The quality of life in individuals with infertility has majorly being along the marginal level, as very small percentage of the respondents had adequate quality of life. This is a call to action for all stakeholders. Every necessary action must be carried out in order to improve the quality of life in individuals with infertility.

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Authors' Contributions

All authors contributed to different aspects of the research.

Conflict of Interest

All the authors hereby declare that they do not have any possible conflicts of interest.

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